

PCR product (pCS1-f 1/pCS2-r 1) XXXGAAAAACGTCCTAGGGTAGCTAAGCTTAAGGATCCAAGGCCGCCACCATGc *ggccgc*agggtgccgaggtggcgtgagcaagggcagggagctgttcxxx
 XXXCTTTTTGCAGGATCCCATCGATTCTGAATTCCATAGTTCCGGCGGTGGTACgat *ccggcgt*ccaccgcctccaccgcactcgttcccgctcctcgcacaagxxx

PCR product (pCS1-f 2/pCS2-r 2) XXXGAAAAACGTCCTAGGGTAGCTAAGCTTAAGGATCCAAGGCCGCCACCATGc *gca*GGTGGCGGAGGTGGCGTGAGCAAGGGCGAGGAGCTGTTCXXX
 XXXCTTTTTGCAGGATCCCATCGATTCTGAATTCCATAGTTCCGGCGGTGGTACgat *cgt*ccaccgcctccaccgcactcgttcccgctcctcgcacaagxxx

denaturation and annealing

Bfal /NotI digested sticky end

XXXGAAAAACGTCCTAGGGTAGCTAAGCTTAAGGATCCAAGGCCGCCACCATGc *ggccgc*agggtgccgaggtggcgtgagcaagggcagggagctgttcxxx
 XXXCTTTTTGCAGGATCCCATCGATTCTGAATTCCATAGTTCCGGCGGTGGTACgat *cgt*ccaccgcctccaccgcactcgttcccgctcctcgcacaagxxx

ligation

